

Artificial intelligence is improving every day, but it comes at a cost: more and more computing power

The omnipresent artificial intelligence

By MARC DURANTON

Artificial intelligence (AI) is everywhere in the news and is the next “big thing” that every company should (and will?) use. It allows the extraction of information from the “big data” that are collected everywhere and will hopefully make a variety of processes more efficient. It can be used in most domains, from medicine to energy, and from smart cities to transportation and manufacturing, and can even be applied to ICT. Officially born at a workshop at Dartmouth College in 1956, it had several “winters” before its last revival in 2012. It has continued to grow ever since. Initially used by web companies to verify content, AI has evolved: it now requires more and more compute power for the “big” systems and can also be used in deeply embedded devices.

Key insights

- AutoML (automated machine learning) is democratizing the development of applications using a deep learning approach, allowing non-specialists to develop their own applications.
- Simulation of virtual environments is starting to be used to generate data for training deep neural networks (for example, NVIDIA’s Metaverse).
- Reinforcement learning approaches, or self-supervised learning techniques, do not need as much data for the learning phase; they only need a reward function or data that provide supervision. They will be more and more used in applications.
- The size of the neural networks that offer the best performance is increasing as a result of that performance, with the consequence that computing power is becoming less and less affordable and accessible and brings with it a sizeable carbon footprint.

Key recommendations

- It is necessary to continue improving the efficiency (in terms of both energy and cost) of the hardware, software and algorithms that are used by deep learning-based AI.
- Make the computational resources that are required for the learning phase of deep learning easily accessible to companies and academics.
- Research and development of tools that help to identify bias and misbehaviour of AI should be developed further.
- Research in Europe could focus on new approaches that do not require a lot of data for learning, and on federated learning approaches that allow privacy to be preserved.
- Europe could focus its efforts on near-the-edge and edge devices, leveraging its knowhow in cyber-physical systems and embedded systems.

The AI bandwagon

Artificial intelligence (AI) is currently marketed as an easy way to exploit big data and large computer infrastructure to improve business processes, with the promise of achieving optimizations to open up even unknown market potential. AI, and more specifically deep learning, was first a necessity for the major technology

companies in the United States (Google, Amazon, Facebook and Apple - GAFA) and in China (Baidu, Alibaba, Tencent and Xiaomi - the BATX). For example, it allowed such companies to check if the millions of pictures uploaded everyday were “correct” (a typical Facebook deep learning use case). They have all the necessary resources: large and powerful comput-

ing infrastructure for learning and managing large databases, large sets of data and ways to attract the best scientists.

But AI is not new: the term Artificial Intelligence was coined by John McCarthy during a workshop at Dartmouth College in 1956 and developed in several directions, the two main ones being:

1956 Dartmouth Conference: The Founding Fathers of AI

John McCarthy

Marvin Minsky

Claude Shannon

Ray Solomonoff

Alan Newell

Herbert Simon

Arthur Samuel

Oliver Selfridge

Nathaniel Rochester

Trenchard More

Image: (Source: https://micro.medium.com/max2400/078MWS6P2QC_WWhmtV)

- Symbolic (or algorithmic) AI where high-level “symbolic” (human-readable) representations of problems are transformed by explicit (logic) rules, generally coming from humans (either directly, applying algorithms, or indirectly, being extracted and organized in expert systems, which use a network of production rules). The “deductions” of the AI system can be therefore followed and explained, but all the “rules” have to be put in the systems beforehand. As computers can process large sets of data quickly, it can create the illusion of “intelligence” because of the size and the speed it applies rules/algorithms to the data.
- “Connectionist” or “artificial neural network based” (now extended to deep learning) – AI. Here, simple models of the neurons of the brain – originating from the work of Warren McCulloch and Walter Pitts in 1943 – are assembled in networks. The “neurons” are connected by “weights” to simulate the biological synapses, and the purpose of the network is mainly a result of the various values of the synapses. During a learning phase,

these weights are determined by repetitive presentations of patterns at the input of the network, and what it means at the output. These multiple presentations set the weights so that at the end, the network associates the desired output with the input. This is called “supervised” learning because the inputs are labelled with the correct responses the neural network should give at the output. The resulting neural network is not only an associative memory: it can also give similar results to input data that are “similar” (not too distant) and this is called generalization. It can then classify (during what is called the “inference” phase) input patterns it has never seen during the learning phase.

There are also other ways to train those neural networks without a supervised approach (for example, with unsupervised learning, where the network determines its output from different inputs which then do not need to be labelled and tries to automatically discriminate entries into different classes, or with reinforcement learning, which focuses on predicting a reward.

Self-supervised learning is another of the possible options). Reinforcement learning was used to train the AlphaGo program and its successors, like Alpha Zero, which, in a few hours and without any knowledge of the field except the rules, beats all its predecessors (and humans) both at the game of Go and at chess. The latest update, MuZero, did not even have to be taught the rules; it observes the results of its actions and therefore improves itself. “The new system tries first one action, then another, learning what the rules allow, at the same time noticing the rewards that are proffered—in chess, by delivering checkmate; in Pac-Man, by swallowing a yellow dot. It then alters its methods until it hits on a way to win such rewards more readily—that is, it improves its play. Such learning by observation is ideal for any AI that faces problems that can’t be specified easily” [29]. “MuZero algorithm, which, by combining a tree-based search with a learned model, achieves superhuman performance in a range of challenging and visually complex domains, without any knowledge of their underlying dynamics.

Hype Cycle for Emerging Technologies, 2020

gartner.com/SmarterWithGartner

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Figure 1: The 2020 hype curve, where AI techniques are very present [8]

The MuZero algorithm learns an iterable model that produces predictions relevant to planning: the action-selection policy, the value function and the reward” [28]. Other approaches are also being developed, such as generative adversarial networks (GANs) that put different networks in competition.

The renaissance of AI in 2012 was triggered by the superior performance of the deep learning approach (a special form of formal neural networks) for image classification, initiated by the work of Hinton et al. in that same year with their “deep

neural network they called “Supervision”. As deep learning provides relatively good (or, at least, good enough) results when applied to various application domains, with relatively low human effort, it has really taken off since then; now it is at the top of the curve of expectations. From a marketing point of view, companies feel obliged to apply these technologies to their products to keep up with the trend. Even methods and approaches that have been used for some time are now jostling for position under the umbrella of “artificial intelligence”. As it does every year, Gartner

has published its “Hype Cycle for Emerging Technologies”, and, without surprises, AI is very present in the 2020 edition.

Deep learning provided breakthroughs in terms of analyzing unstructured data such as images and sound, as well as allowing an efficient interface between computers and the world, facilitating cyber-physical applications. This has really opened up possibilities for new solutions and business propositions, like self-driving cars, personal assistants and so on.

A brief history of Deep Learning (From HiPEAC vision 2019, pp.23-24)

Throughout history, people have sought to make machines that amplify their physical, then mental abilities. The brain was not always considered the centre of intelligence: Aristotle believed that it was only used to cool the heart. However, the approach advocated by Plato, Hippocrates and Democritus, for whom the brain was the centre of awareness of sensations and the guardian of intelligence, finally prevailed and many generations of researchers have sought, and still seek to analyse its functioning. The idea of imitating it to make “intelligent” systems is not new, but it was the discoveries of the 20th century that triggered the first results.

Drawing on the knowledge of biologists of their time, in 1943 Warren Sturgis McCulloch, an American neurologist, and Walter Pitts, a mathematician and psychologist, proposed a mathematical model of the simplified functioning of biological neurons, cells which form one of the components of the brain. Their paper, “A Logical Calculus of Ideas Immanent in Nervous Activity”, was published in 1943 in the “Bulletin of Mathematical Biophysics” (5:115-133) and remains the basis of formal neural networks. Their model is simple: a neuron performs a binary function that compares the weighted sum of its inputs (connected to the other neurons) to a threshold.

They have shown that a sufficiently complex network can “calculate” any function. John von Neumann, whose “First Draft of a Report on the EDVAC” is considered to be the first description of a modern computer (von Neumann’s machine) cites only this McCulloch and Pitts paper in this 1945 report and infers from McCulloch and Pitts’ article that “everything that can be described exhaustively and unambiguously... can be conceived as an appropriate neural network”. It confirms that a neural network can represent a universal Turing machine, and therefore a universal calculator. Unfortunately, the limitations

of the technology of the time did not allow him to develop the highly parallel approach of neural networks, and thus it resulted in an architecture with memory, a control unit, an arithmetic unit and input and output units, which are found in today’s computers.

In 1957, psychologist Frank Rosenblatt invented an algorithm called a “perceptron”. For this classifier, the weighting between neurons is inspired by the Hebb rule, which considers that when two neurons are excited together, their link is strengthened. The perceptron rule takes into account the observed error when propagating an input whose output function is calculated by the perceptron. The first winter of neural networks was caused by Marvin Minsky and Seymour Papert’s book *Perceptrons: an introduction to computational geometry*, which shows limitations of perceptrons. The 1986 book *Parallel Distributed Processing: Explorations in the Microstructure of Cognition* by David Everett Rumelhart and James McClelland relaunched the field with a testable approach of multi-layer networks (essentially with an intermediate layer, called the “hidden layer”) called multi-layer-perceptrons (MLPs).

A learning rule (called gradient retro-propagation) for calculating the weights of intermediate layers was published in his thesis in 1985 by Yann LeCun (now at Facebook), then widely distributed by David Rumelhart, Geoffrey Hinton (now at Google Brain) and Ronald Williams in 1986. This led to an initial explosion in the use of neural networks in the 1990s. They were used for the recognition of handwritten characters (to recognize postcodes), for image analysis etc. A first era of specialized circuit development followed, but the techniques of the time allowed only limited parallelism, and the rapid advance of general-purpose processors limited their expansion.

The uptake of support vector machine (SVM) then signalled the beginning of a new winter of neural networks by offering better perfor-

mance than MLPs for image classification. The principles were explored between 1963 and 1970 by Vladimir Vapnik, but it was only in 1992 that an article by Boser, Guyon and Vapnik synthesized the results and allowed broad development of SVMs for classification.

Meanwhile, neural networks became deeper (with more layers), thanks to methods allowing the use of back-propagation approaches to gradient networks with more than one hidden layer. The networks became more complex, specializing the layers as in the visual cortex. The results of neuroscientists David Marr, David Hubel and Torsten Wiesel (the latter two were awarded the Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine in 1981 for their discoveries concerning information processing in the visual system) inspired researchers to make networks more suitable for object recognition. Their predecessor is the “neocognitron” invented in the 1980s by Kunihiko Fukushima. Deep convolutional networks as currently used are more than 20 years old, but thanks to the dramatic increase of data availability and computer power, more complex networks are now possible, which unlock a complete new range of performance.

The most recent renaissance was brought about in 2012 by Alex Krizhevsky, Ilya Sutskever and Geoffrey Hinton, who used deep convolutional neural networks for the ImageNet challenge, which consists in classifying images in the ImageNet image database. The Hinton Supervision Network beats the other approaches with an error rate of 15.3% compared to 26.1% for the second. From 2013, the top eight approaches in the challenge are based on deep neural networks. Indeed, deep networks are better than a human on this challenge (human level was estimated at 5% errors, according to the work of Andrej Karpathy), with less than 3.5% errors. The following table shows the very rapid improvement of deep learning algorithms, until being better than humans.

Figure 2: From [11]

TECHNICAL DIMENSION

Figure 3: From [10]

The size (and compute requirement) of deep learning networks are growing exponentially

Thanks to the fact that a deep network is formed by learning and not explicitly programmed, it can be applied in many applications where it is difficult to explicitly define an algorithm, such as in image recognition (essential for autonomous vehicles), speech comprehension (all personal assistants, from Siri to Alexa or Google Now, use deep networks, often recursive), lip reading and participation in various games. A large “labelled” (indexed) database is all that is needed; these are often available from major internet players (Google, Baidu, Facebook, Microsoft, Apple, etc.), explaining why they conduct in-depth research on learning. For example, several billion photos pass every day through two types of deep networks at Facebook, Instagram, Messenger, WhatsApp for image/index recognition and facial recognition (although these are not enabled in Europe).

Networks and techniques are becoming more complex, combining several approaches. For example, the AlphaGo program developed by Google DeepMind beat Lee Sedol (a 9-dan professional in the Go game) in March 2016, generating a lot of publicity for deep learning and AI techniques.

In general, there are two phases in the use of deep networks: the learning phase, in which the network parameters (connection weights) are determined by the learning rule, and the inference phase in which the network is used to classify the data. The learning phase is the most demanding, with millions or billions of example presentations and changes in network settings. It is now generally done on 16-bit floating point graphics processing units (GPUs) (even if recent research seems to show that 4-bits might be enough [12]) or on specialized circuits such as Google’s Tensor Processing Units (TPUs) [23]. The inference phase is less demanding and can be performed with less precision (integer, even reduced to 8-bits, or even lower, down to two states). It is usually this phase that is implemented in embedded devices for image recognition, etc. Synaptic weights

are downloaded after learning and can be updated after a new learning, extending the number of recognized objects.

For example, Supervision, the network developed by the University of Toronto’s Geoffrey Hinton and colleagues is composed of 650,000 artificial neurons connected by 630,000,000 shared connections (synapses). On today’s networks, the learning stage could require a few exaFLOPS (more than a billion billion operations). Figure 3 shows the exponential increase of compute power required by the most advanced neural networks, roughly by x10 per year (to be compared to Moore’s law – the observation that the number of transistors in a dense integrated circuit doubles about every two years).

This exponential growth* is confirmed in 2020, with GPT-3 [15], a system for natural language processing (NLP) using the “transformer” approach that has 175 billion parameters (the largest GPT-3 model – with 175B parameters – uses 96 attention layers, each with 96x128-dimension heads). *“GPT-3 175B model required 3.14x10²³ FLOPS (so about 87h of an exascale machine – 10¹⁸ floating point operations per second) of computing for training. Even at theoretical 28 TFLOPS for V100 and lowest 3 year reserved cloud pricing we could find, this will take 355 GPU-years and cost \$4.6M for a single training run. Similarly, a single RTX 8000, assuming 15 TFLOPS, would take 665 years to run”* [2].

However, GPT-3 shows amazing results in a lot of domains, from completing text, to translation or to even generating correct code from high level textural specifications [14].

“GPT-3 shows that language model performance scales as a power-law of model size, dataset size, and the amount of computation... GPT-3 demonstrates that a language model trained on enough data can solve NLP tasks that it has never encountered. That is, GPT-3 studies the model as a general solution for many downstream jobs without fine-tuning... GPT-3 175B is trained with 499 Billion tokens” [2].

Dataset	# Tokens (Billions)
Total	499
Common Crawl (filtered by quality)	410
WebText2	19
Books1	12
Books2	55
Wikipedia	3

We see now a race for bigger and bigger neural networks, Microsoft already released DeepSpeed, that “adapts to the varying needs of workload requirements to power extremely large models with over a trillion parameters while achieving near-perfect memory-scaling and throughput-scaling efficiency” [15]. DeepSpeed, using a machine with a single NVIDIA V100 GPU, can run models of up to 13 billion parameters without running out of memory.

We are even beginning to see research using deep learning approaches to create other, more optimized, deep learning networks. This is called AutoML. “AutoML open-source tools automate the entire life cycle of ideating, conceptualization, development, and deployment of predictive models. From data preparation through model training to validation as well as deployment, these tools do everything with almost zero human intervention” [16]. AutoML can facilitate the use of deep learning, allowing even non-specialists to develop advanced application quasi automatically. All major companies such as Amazon (AutoGluon), Google (cloud autoML) and Microsoft (Azure) are providing AutoML tools to their users. However, some techniques used in AutoML (like design space exploration) are also large consumers of processing power.

If AutoML is democratizing the development of applications using deep learning, the user still has to provide a large database of data to train the networks (if using supervised learning approach). This can be solved by creating data sets through simulation in a real-life like environment. For example, NVIDIA’s Omniverse environment allows the creation of a photorealistic environment to train and simulate various AI [17].

* Since the writing of this article, Google Brain announced its Switch Transformer Language Model that packs 1.6 trillion parameters!

These virtual environments also allow the validation of AIs that use smaller data sets or only “reward” functions like for reinforcement learning or in self-supervised learning, which is a form of unsupervised learning where the data provides the supervision (for example, by withholding some part of the data, and the task of the network is to predict it).

It should be noted that, in terms of tools and software for developing deep neural networks, the major players in the field provide their development tools as free software. Examples include TensorFlow (Google), CNTK (Microsoft), DSSTNE (Amazon), Theano, Caffe (Berkeley) and Caffe2, Torch (Facebook) and PyTorch (Python interface), N2D2 (CEA), Torchnet learning modules, OpenAi Gym (Open AI), MXNet, etc. In fact, software is a non-critical element in creating an effective system of in-depth learning. A large database and neural network topology are

Figure 4: Nvidia Omniverse [6]

the main ingredients: the value lies in the neural network topology and its weights, determined after learning on a particular database, not in the software that executes it – which should be optimized to use less resources and energy. But advances in models and algorithms allow for the

reduction of the complexity of the neural networks; their improvement is therefore a key factor driving progress in AI: “Since 2012 the amount of compute needed to train a neural net to the same performance on ImageNet1 classification has been decreasing by a factor of 2 every 16 months” [3].

Figure 5: Decrease of performance needed to carry out a similar AI task over time [3]

However, a comparison of Figure 5 and Figure 3 clearly shows that the computing power requirement is still greatly exceeding the algorithmic improvement, and even exceeding the combination of algorithmic improvement and improvement of the hardware and software (better dedicated architectures, Moore’s law, better integration processing and storage, better tools, etc.). This has several direct implications:

- It is necessary to continue improving the hardware, software and algorithms that are used by deep learning-based AI. Pruning networks, using computing with less numerical precision (decreasing the numbers of bits), or even using other ways to code information, like spiking networks (where the information is carried by a model of the “spike” signals like the ones used in biological neurons) are ways to improve efficiency. Using sparsity, and computing and moving data when it is really necessary, are approaches to improve the overall efficiency of computing systems. (“Spike” computing, even implemented in digital systems, is a way to realize sparsity of computation, because the information is coded “in time”, and the more “spikes” that are processed, the more accurate the results. The system can therefore dynamically stop computing when accuracy is good enough to give meaningful results, unlike binary coding where all bits are always processed). Finding more or less automated ways to reduce the size of computation [12], using more efficient existing hardware [13] and optimizing networks to target architecture [19,20,21] form an active domain of research and development, together with the development of new hardware accelerators.
- It is also obvious that the energy consumption of those systems is also becoming increasingly problematic, as laid out in [26,27] (“Training a single AI model can emit as much carbon as five cars in their lifetimes”), leading to further need for improvement of the energy efficiency of deep learning systems. However, the learning is done once, and if the resulting system can be reused in inference millions of times and for several applications, the energy consumed during training should be offset by the gains the system brings during its use.

Figure 6: Increasing parallelism makes it possible to train more complex models in a reasonable amount of time. A Pareto frontier chart is the most intuitive way to visualize comparisons between algorithms and scales [4]

- The computing resources required for training those gigantic networks are no longer available to most research centres or industry settings. As of the end of 2020, the most powerful supercomputer in Europe – 7th in the TOP500 list – has a processing power of about 44 petaFLOPS (44.1015 FLOPS), so it would take about 82 days at full capacity to train GPT-3 (according to the figure provided by [2]). It therefore seems that, in practice, only the giant companies like Google, Amazon (with its AWS infrastructure) or Microsoft (with Azure) have the required processing capabilities in the western world. Research centres are either acquired (Deepmind is part of Google) or closely linked with those companies (OpenAi has a deal with Microsoft [22]). Moreover, the computing requirements of AI are so large that those companies are all developing hardware accelerators to boost performance. This was pioneered by Google with its line of TPU chips (they are on their 4th generation, which are on average 2.5x better performing than the previous generation [23]), followed by Amazon (AWS Inferentia [24]) and Microsoft (using Graphcore accelerators, but planning to develop their own chips as well [25]).

The level of investment required to explore the capabilities of huge neural networks, which indeed offer surprising even if not flawless [14] performance, is so high that it might limit their evolution to take place only within large companies or state entities. Not everybody is able to pay \$4.6M for training GPT-3, or invest in the development of complex chip accelerators or farms of servers. The move of OpenAI from an “open” model to a commercial one with Microsoft is an example. The dilemma of computing power, time and cost is illustrated well in Figure 6.

Artificial intelligence: strategy for companies and for countries

As shown earlier in this article and in the HiPEAC Vision 2019 (pp. 21-20), artificial intelligence is becoming both a strategic asset for companies and a topic of sovereignty for countries. AI could create a “winner takes all” phenomenon: the first results from AI will result in economic benefits, then a quasi-monopolistic status because the AI-designed approach will allow greater profit margins, so that the winner could reduce prices and kill the competition until it achieves a monopoly. Countries like the United States, China and Japan are launching major AI projects, confident that new breakthroughs will

occur and will have a profound impact on our society in the years to come. Russia's President Putin has said the nation that leads in AI "will be the ruler of the world". China is making huge investments in AI and is feared by the US, which is also starting to invest heavily in AI. In contrast to China, in the US most activity around AI is currently undertaken by the major technology companies (GAFAM), which are also draining universities in the rest of the world of AI experts. A list of AI initiatives in different countries can be found in [7].

Besides being strategic for countries, AI is also a growing market for business, and IDC forecasts that "worldwide revenues for the artificial intelligence (AI) market, including software, hardware, and services, are expected to total \$156.5 billion in 2020, an increase of 12.3% over 2019. [...] A new forecast from the IDC Worldwide

Semiannual Artificial Intelligence Tracker shows worldwide revenues surpassing \$300 billion in 2024 with a five-year compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 17.1%" [30].

Edge AI and federation of devices: the position of Europe

What could the position of Europe in this international landscape of AI be? Europe does not have the big B2C companies that can harvest large quantities of consumer data and develop large computing infrastructure. However, it has several assets: its educational system trains good researchers and specialists in AI (who unfortunately, are often attracted to work outside Europe (brain drain) because of better working conditions such as access to computing power, databases, etc.) and its knowhow in cyber-physical systems and embedded systems. Therefore, if Europe reacts fast because the competition

is fierce, it can be leading in artificial intelligence at the edge, leveraging its assets in embedded systems. In the short term, it could use corporate or institutional data (from cities, electric and water networks, hospitals, etc.) to optimize its processes and manage solutions and services at the edge. It can also apply its privacy-related ethics to AI systems that do not centralize private data on cloud servers, but are based on a federation of smaller and distributed systems. "Federated Learning is a machine learning procedure where the goal is to train a high-quality model with data distributed over several independent providers. Instead of gathering the data on a single central server, the data remains locked on their server, and the algorithms and predictive models travel between them" [31].

Figure 7: International strategies on AI [7]

The recommendation of HiPEAC Vision 2019 still holds in 2021:

If one day, artificial general intelligence becomes a reality, and if that artificial general intelligence is more powerful than human intelligence, Europe will only be able to compete with the rest of the world by building ever smarter computing systems. Instead of the war for talent (fought by companies, universities and countries), in order to improve competitiveness, Europe will have to invest in intelligent systems that will help create better products and do better research. There is a belief that “the future information society will not be built on human brains but on artificial brains”. The societal values of Europe should be built into systems, in order to ensure its future existence.

HiPEAC Vision 2019, p.22

According to a prediction by Forbes, the total number of academic research papers published on federated learning will surge. “Data privacy is becoming an increasingly urgent issue for consumers and regulators.

Given this, privacy-preserving AI methods will continue to gain momentum as the most sustainable way to build machine learning models. The most prominent of these methods is federated learning. The number of academic research papers published on federated learning has grown from 254 in 2018, to 1,340 in 2019, to 3,940 in 2020, according to Google Scholar. This exponential growth will continue: in 2021, over 10,000 research papers will be published on the topic of federated learning” [18]. Europe has without doubt a central role to play in this field.

Research in Europe could also focus on new approaches that don't require large volumes of data for learning, such as self-supervised learning, reinforcement learning or systems like MuZero that learn by observation [28].

In terms of hardware, Europe could focus its effort on near-the-edge and edge devices, relying on its semiconductor manufacturers and start-ups that are well positioned in the embedded space. Systems for self-driving vehicles or ADAS,

or for edge computing have a large and very diverse market, requiring a multiplicity of different uses and modes of application. The landscape is large, as shown in Figure 8.

Explainability and/or transparency of AI: importance of ethical AI

One of the main complaints about machine learning, particularly deep learning, is that its models are opaque, non-intuitive, and difficult for people to understand and that the machines are unable to “explain” their decisions, leading to a lack of confidence and trust in the system. Its results can also be totally different when altering just a small part of its input, such as a few pixels in an image (this is called “adversarial attacks”). This is an important problem, leading to new kinds of piracy tuned to this kind of processing. To address this, there are few developing fields of research concerning deep neural networks:

- Explainable AI (especially for deep neural networks);
- Creation of robust solutions which are impervious to deliberately introduced fake data;

Figure 8: The chip landscape [9]

- Detection of bias in the learning data sets that could lead to unethical responses of the deep learning systems;
- Design of systems that can assess the likelihood of their results.

The explainability of the results of deep learning is an important topic in terms of the acceptability of technology solutions, but should not be taken too far; by way of comparison, there are a number of industrial processes that are not fully understood but this does not prevent them being used in everyday life. Processes of certification and validation can be used to ensure a certain “trust” in the system without everything about it being understood. The process of how the system is built and tested in the field might be enough in certain cases (for example, you trust a taxi driver because he has a licence, and you do not have to open his brain to see how it

is working). What is more important is to ensure that a deep learning neural network effectively learns what it is supposed to learn, and not anything else.

It is therefore very important to develop approaches and tools to check that the learning databases are free from bias, whether introduced deliberately or accidentally. This is perhaps easier to achieve than full “explainability” of deep learning decisions, which is important but will be difficult to achieve without clear breakthroughs.

The most important points are to ensure that the specifications that lead to the learning databases are as complete and exhaustive as possible, with minimum bias, and to check after learning that the system has learnt only what it was supposed to learn, rather than other artefacts present

in the learning database. It is also important to expose the system to counter examples, that is, things it should not do. Most of the time, designers focus on what the system should do (recognition rate) and not on what it should not do (false alarm). Sometimes, modern databases are “too good”, with only clear images, making the system more sensitive to noise or other artificially introduced artefacts. With this “classical approach” of supervised learning, humans are still in the loop and ultimately responsible for the design of the learning database, therefore also responsible for the resulting deep network and what it will do in the inference phase. Research and development of tools that help to identify bias and misbehaviour of AI should be developed further.

Another idea to consider is that of not using deep learning alone for a task, but combining several approaches (including other deep learning solutions or symbolic ones) and adding a kind of supervisory process that checks whether the results are coherent. If fed with totally random input, a deep neural network will still give results, which are of course not relevant. The system should be able to indicate if its results are relevant/correct or not, and be able to generate an “I don’t know” answer.

Legal liability in the event of an AI system failure is important, but, in the case of deep learning, it applies more to the initial specifications and definition of the learning database (done by humans – at least for now) than to how the deep learning system works by itself. Because humans are at the origin of the algorithms or the learning database, they should ultimately be held responsible in the event of errors by artificial intelligence. The main problem will be to identify potential errors, and to be able to correct them.

Needless to say, as shown in the Figure 9, humans are also prone to error (such as optical illusions) and sometimes have difficulty checking whether a system is unrealistic.

Figure 9: Unlike what it seems, the checkerboard boxes A and B are of the exact same shade of grey: see below

THE 5TH RESEARCH PARADIGM?

The convergence of simulation, machine learning and knowledge allows the emergence of a 5th paradigm in science and technology: as explained in the HiPEAC Vision 2019: “The first three paradigms were experimental (empirical description of phenomena), theoretical (discovery of laws, models, etc. able to predict results) and, more recently, computational science (computer simulations). The fourth paradigm of scientific discovery is the analysis of massive data sets, enabled, e.g. by data capture, curation, mining and analytics techniques and thus permitting new scientific discoveries.

In the fourth paradigm, computers are used to extract information from raw data, but it is still humans who perform the analysis of the information and make the scientific discovery. We believe that within the next decade there will be a fifth paradigm, in which computers will be not only extract information from data, but will also formulate a hypothesis, design new experiments and simulations or make a formal proof and finally make scientific discoveries without human intervention. We already have examples of this with formal provers, data analytics, and approaches like IBM’s Watson. Potentially, the Ultra-Intelligent machine could solve problems that are beyond the reach of human intelligence”

HiPEAC Vision 2017 pp.59

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